

Serbian Biochemical Society

President: Marija Gavrović-Jankulović

Vice-president: Suzana Jovanović-Šanta

General Secretary: Isidora Protić-Rosić

Treasurer: Milica Popović

Scientific Board

Marija Gavrović-
Jankulović
Svetlana Dinić
Ario de Marco
Suzana Jovanović-
Šanta
Mario Gabričević
Vladimir Mihailović
Theodore G.
Sotiroudis

Natalija Polović
Andreja Rajković
Nataša Simin
Edvard Petri
Sanja Krstić
Željko Popović
Snežana Pantović
Milan Nikolić
Simeon Minić

Organization Committee

Ivan Spasojević
Tanja Ćirković
Veličković
Milica Popović
Aleksandra
Uskoković
Tijana Ćulafić
Isidora Protić-Rosić
Jovana Trbojević-Ivić
Milena Dimitrijević
Srđan Miletić

Proceedings

Editor: Ivan Spasojević

Technical support: Jovana Trbojević-Ivić, Milena Dimitrijević, Tijana Ćulafić

Cover design: Zoran Beloševac

Publisher: Faculty of Chemistry, Serbian Biochemical Society

Printed by: Colorgrafx, Belgrade

No of printed copies: 130

Serbian Biochemical Society
Twelfth Conference

International scientific meeting

September 21-23, 2023, Belgrade, Serbia

“Biochemistry in Biotechnology”

Foreword

Dear colleagues

Welcome to the XII Conference of The Serbian Biochemical Society, entitled 'Biochemistry in Biotechnology'.

This year we have the richest program ever. In addition to our tradition to invite promising young researchers from four main university centers in Serbia to deliver lectures, we have eight guests from abroad that will participate through FEBS3+ program or within ANSO PRESSION project. This is a turning point in the organization of the conference which undergoes a transformation into scientific event with strong international character.

As always, we cherish the participation of PhD students and early career researchers. We are glad that many colleagues took the opportunity to show what they do and to find their place within the scientific ecosystem.

Organizing Committee

Influence of bile acids and their derivatives on drug transport into central nervous system

Marija Gvoić^{1*}, Saša Vukmirović¹, Bojan Stanimirov², Karmen Stankov²

¹*Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

**e-mail: 1109d16@mf.uns.ac.rs; m_skendzic@yahoo.com.*

Primary brain tumors as well as central nervous system (CNS) metastases are in focus of clinical and scientific interest because of the complexity of their treatment due to their location behind the blood-brain barrier (BBB). The main obstacle for efficacy of antitumor drugs in treatment of brain tumors is their low penetrance across the BBB and decreased drug delivery to malignant cells. Previously published results of our scientific group show that bile acids (BAs) and their derivatives have impact on improvement of the absorption, bioavailability and pharmacodynamic of several drugs^{1,2}. In addition, current preliminary results of our group provides the evidence supporting the claim that antitumor drugs have the ability to cross the BBB when administered with BAs. That ability can be exploited by taking a part in novel drug carrier designs. BAs represent a drug carrier system as a part of a mixed micelle composition, bilosomes and conjugates with various drugs. Modern strategies addressed to this issue comprize intranasal drug administration, ligand conjugation, BBB disruption and use of BAs and nanomaterials for CNS drug delivery. Our present research discusses the current knowledge related to bile acid molecules as drug penetration modifying agents, with the focus on central nervous system antitumor drug delivery.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the grant from Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia III41012 (Grant No. 451-03-47/2023-01/200114), and Project of special interest for sustainable development in the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina (Grant No. 142-451-2532/2021-01).

References

1. Gvoic M, Vukmirovic S, Al-Salami H, Mooranian A, Mikov M, Stankov K. Bile acids as novel enhancers of CNS targeting antitumor drugs: A comprehensive review. *Pharm Dev Technol* 2021;26617-33.
2. Vasović V, et al. Influence of bile acid derivates on morphine analgesic effect in mice. *Vojnosanitetski Pregled* 2014;71:767-71.